

Student's consent

 Mandatory questions are marked with a star (*)

DigiTala project 2019-2023 | Academy of Finland | University of Helsinki, University of Jyväskylä, Aalto University

CONSENT OF RESEARCH PARTICIPANT

I have been asked to participate in the DigiTala research project funded by the Academy of Finland. I have received sufficient information about the research and its purpose, the content and use of the material, including the processing and storage of personal data.

By filling this form, I confirm that I have received [the information sheet for research participants](#) and [privacy notice](#) (helsinki.fi/en/digitala/privacy)

I understand that participation in this research is voluntary. I have the right to discontinue participation in the research at any time. I am not required to state the reason for the withdrawal and there will be no negative consequences.

Contact information

1. Name *

First name

Surname

2. Contact information

Will not be given outside the research project and will only be used for research-related communication.

Telephone

Email *

3. Name of school *

4. Gender

- Woman
- Man
- Other
- Prefer not to answer

5. Age

- 15-21
- 22-26
- 27-60
- 61 or older

Consent

6. My information may be used in the DigiTala research. *

- I give permission
- I do not give permission

7. The research material may later be combined with the results of the language tests in the Matriculation Examination *

- I give permission
- I do not give permission

8. Date of birth

Needed for a follow-up study: Write your date of birth in format dd.mm.yyyy or select it on the calendar.

Date of birth

9. I may be contacted when follow-up on the research is planned (feedback, interviews) *

- I give permission
- I do not give permission

10. My speech samples may be published for research or educational purposes for teachers and raters (without name / school / contact information) *

- I give permission
- I do not give permission

11. The research material may be permanently stored in the Language Bank of Finland and it may be used in other research related to language learning (without name, including speech samples) *

- I give permission
- I do not give permission

Language background

12. First language(s)

- Swedish
- Finnish
- Russian
- Somali
- Estonian
- English
- Arabic
- Persian
- Kurdish

- Chinese
- Vietnamese
- Other, please specify _____

13. How many modules (/courses) have you studied Finnish in the upper secondary school?

Please answer with a number

14. According to which syllabus have you studied Finnish?

- Finnish as a second language and literature
- Finnish, native-level (mofi)
- Finnish, advanced syllabus (A Finnish)
- Finnish, intermediate syllabus (B1 Finnish)
- Finnish, basic syllabus (B3 Finnish, started in the upper secondary school)
- I don't know / I'm not sure

15. What other languages do you speak / have studied?

- Albanian
- Arabic
- Bengali
- Dari
- English
- Spanish
- Italian
- Chinese
- Kurdish
- Nepalese

- Portuguese
- Polish
- French
- Romanian
- German
- Somali
- Finnish
- Thai
- Turkish
- Ukrainian
- Hungarian
- Urdu
- Russian
- Vietnamese
- Estonian
- Other, please specify _____

16. Comments

17. As a reward for my participation in the research

- I want to receive a gift card to R-kioski (value 10e, code will be sent to your email address)
- I do not want a gift